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ATTITUDE OF STUDENTS TOWARDS MODERN APPROACHES OF BLENDED AND FLIPPED LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

Being a very advanced learning format, blended learning involves both offline and online learning activities within the same discipline or course. Flipped learning is a model of blended learning when a passive format of lectures is delegated to independent work before a full-time meeting with the teaching staff. Thus, the phase of active learning is expanded and the effectiveness of full-time work in the audience increases, since offline work hours are redistributed into active learning formats. This study focuses on students' perception and attitude of blended and flipped learning as a university teaching format. The paper also discusses the issues of motivation of students with the aim of more extensive implementation of these formats in the educational programs of Russian universities.

Students of Tomsk State University of Control Systems and Radioelectronics (TUSUR), Tomsk, Russia, had to answer a series of questions on the formats of online learning and offer recommendations to overcome the limitations of these learning approaches. Overall, the study aims for analysis of students' attitudes while discussing the following questions: (1) What is the difference between blended and flipped learning approaches? Which approach is more effective? (2) How are blended learning formats useful for students? (3) How can students be encouraged and motivated to engage themselves in a flipped learning format? (4) How can students be motivated in choosing flipped courses, provided that these disciplines are not in the study plan?

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1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Paper Summary

Flipped learning is seen as a model of blended learning when a passive format of lectures is delegated to independent work before a full-time meeting with the teacher staff. This is basically the difference between flipped and conventional offline learning approaches. The material is studied by students independently before the start of the lesson with the help of diverse ICT aides (video lectures, interactive elements, online presentations). All this results into a greater time resource during an offline class that could be aimed at hands-on tasks: solving problems, group interaction, team work. Thus, the phase of active learning is expanded and the effectiveness of full-time work in the audience increases, since offline work hours are redistributed into active learning formats. Flipped learning model assumes that the direct instruction is shifted from the group learning space to the individual learning space transforming the group learning space into a dynamic, interactive and creative environment [1]. This study presents the results of the joint work of the focus group of university students on the issue of discussing modern formats of blended and flipped learning. Also, the paper discusses the issues of motivation of students to be engaged in flipped learning courses with the aim of more extensive implementation of these formats in the educational programs of Russian universities.

1.2 Blended vs. Flipped learning

Blended learning usually implies the combination of offline and online educational approaches. This type of learning, by its essence, is not limited to technical issues or distance-learning students, but it represents an effective combination of educational content delivery modes as well as diversity of teaching models and learning styles [2]. A flipped classroom is a teaching methodology that makes part of the blended learning approach when a traditional class setting is inverted shifting lecture and some other study materials outside the class [3]. Implementation of flipped classrooms is documented as a beneficial instructional design with positive responses from students [4]. Despite this fact, there are some discrepancies in students' perception of flipped learning, learning outcomes compared with traditionally delivered classes, and the role of educators in facilitation of the learning process [5].

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Rationale for the study

A vast majority of offline courses at Tomsk State University of Control Systems and Radioelectronics are supplemented with online course modules on the Moodle platform, so students of the university are considered to have a high degree of awareness in terms of online education. Also, they are usually seen as being fully equipped with the knowledge and skills for blended learning. Therefore, educators envisage the situation with joining together offline and online educational activities as an efficient way to enhance leaning outcomes. As a rationale of this study we

assumed the necessity to investigate awareness and attitude of the students towards flipped classrooms, which make part of blended learning.

2.2 Design of the Study

The focus group of chosen 4 participants for the present study possess some experience in preparing educational materials for the flipped course “Innovation Systems and Technological Development”, which is being developed at TUSUR as a part of the CEPHEI - Industrial E-Learning project supported by the Erasmus + program. Also, the participants of the focus group have 2 years of experience of participation in blended learning courses at TUSUR on the Moodle platform.

Students of TUSUR, Tomsk, Russia, had to answer a series of questions on the formats of online learning and offer recommendations to overcome the limitations of these learning approaches. Overall, the study aims for analysis of students' attitudes while discussing the following questions:

(Q1) What is the difference between blended and flipped learning approaches? Which approach is more effective?

(Q2) How are blended learning formats useful for students?

(Q3) How can students be encouraged and motivated to engage themselves in a flipped learning format?

(Q4) How can students be motivated in choosing flipped courses, provided that these disciplines are not in the study plan?

3 RESULTS

3.1 (Q1) What is the difference between blended and flipped learning approaches? Which approach is more effective?

Despite the fact that the students of the focus group have sufficient experience in online learning, it turned out to be a difficult task for them to specify the characteristics and differences of these two educational online formats. Students generally highlighted the benefits of blended learning through opportunities to reduce study time through self-study, possibility to consult with teachers when needed, and help on behalf of educators in prioritization of study materials key points.

3.2 (Q2) How are blended learning formats useful for students?

Students noted that thanks to blended learning, the knowledge foundation is being developed on the necessary topics. Moreover, it becomes possible to independently distribute and re-distribute time for educational tasks. As a crucial point, it was mentioned that the blended learning format significantly contributes to enhance skills of independent work and self-study. Students emphasized importance of blended learning in acquiring skills of analysis and systematization as well as critical thinking and systemic thinking. Skills of time management are also being developed.

3.3 (Q3) How can students be encouraged and motivated to engage themselves in a flipped learning format?

Among the ways of motivation that can encourage students to take flipped learning courses are: (1) a system of automatic passes, which is subject to the strict study rules and deadlines if a course is delivered in the blended (flipped) learning format; (2) a rigorous disciplinary approach using the “stick and carrot” method; (3) a long-term strategic decision to foster discipline from childhood in favour of responsible behaviour and a change in mentality; (4) the introduction of a collective (group/team) responsibility regime in case of non-compliance with the rules of the game when working within the framework in the format of flipped learning.

3.4 (Q4) How can students be motivated in choosing flipped courses, provided that these disciplines are not in the study plan?

The proposals included: (1) spreading word of mouth, provided that the course in this format is already a successful educational product; (2) a creative and unusual approach to the presentation of the study materials that requires a creative approach from a course developer or a teacher (as triggers are seen the following: a breathtaking introductory lecture, an interesting life story, entertaining cases with discussions at the start of the course); (3) reputation of the teacher or course developer that already implies the existence of the previously acquired experience and reputation as a valuable asset.

4 SUMMARY AND ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Overall, the current research results received from a small focus group will be used to develop a semi-structured survey to continue the study with the presented research questions for an enlarged audience of Tomsk university students to verify research outcomes.

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